

Project Title	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC
Project Acronym	FAIR-IMPACT
Grant Agreement No.	101057344
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	www.fair-impact.eu

D1.4 - Sustainability Plan

Work Package	WP1, Project management, synchronisation and sustainability
Lead Author (Org)	Ingrid Dillo (DANS)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Maaïke Verburg (DANS), Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC), Clement Jonquet (INRAE), Sophie Aubin (INRAE), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Wim Hugo (DANS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Anne Sofie Fink (DeiC), Morane Gruenpeter (INRIA)
Due Date	2025-05-31
Date	2025-05-23
Version	V1.0 - draft not yet approved by the EC
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15497233

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	2025.02.04	Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	TOC according to output inventory
0.5	2025.04.18	Ingrid Dillo (DANS), Maaïke Verburg (DANS), Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC), Clément Jonquet (INRAE), Sophie Aubin (INRAE), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Wim Hugo (DANS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Anne Sofie Fink (DeiC), Morane Gruenpeter (INRIA)	Version ready for internal review
0.6	2025.04.23	Ingrid Dillo (DANS)	Overall internal review
0.7	2025.04.25	Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	Overall internal review
0.8	2025.04.28	Ingrid Dillo (DANS) Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	Version ready for reviewers
0.9	2025.05.20	Maaïke Verburg (DANS), Ingrid Dillo (DANS), Joy Davidson (DCC), Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Clément Jonquet (INRAE)	Reviewer feedback incorporated
1.0	2025.05.23	Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	Final version published on Zenodo

Disclaimer

FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/ Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit; a set of concepts, implemented as a graph database and accessible via APIs, and supported by user interfaces via the APIs developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIF	FAIR Implementation Framework: a set of steps that helps different stakeholder groups assess their drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling and their current practices so that they can develop realistic action and engagement plans to implement FAIR.
KER	Key exploitable results which have been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream in the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.
KF	Key functions are important functions performed by the project which require sustainability measures during and after the project.
KO	Key outputs are results which require sustainability measures during and after the project not selected as a KER.
MAR	Multi-annual roadmap: a section of the EOSC SRIA with the purpose of informing the periodically developed Horizon Europe Work Programmes.
MOD	Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RSMD	Research Software Metadata guidelines
SA	Semantic Artefacts a broad term that includes ontologies, terminologies, taxonomies, thesauri, vocabularies, metadata schemas and standards—were defined by the FAIRsFAIR project and the EOSC Interoperability Framework as: “machine-actionable and readable formalisation of a conceptualisation that enables the sharing and reuse by humans and machines”.
SAC	Semantic Artefact Catalogues a broad term that includes ontology repositories, knowledge organisation systems registries, vocabulary/terminology services and metadata standards/schemas catalogues and registries. SACs are essential tools for the identification, description, evaluation, and exchange of semantic artefacts, enhancing their reuse and alignment.
SRIA	EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda: to define the general framework for future research, development and innovation activities in relation to the European Open Science Cloud.

Executive Summary

*FAIR-IMPACT: Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC*¹ ran from June 2022 to May 2025 and included 28 partners from 11 countries. The project sought to build on the successful practices, policies, tools, and technical specifications arising from FAIRsFAIR,² other Horizon 2020 projects and initiatives,³ and from the EOSC Association Task Forces,⁴ such as the one on FAIR metrics and data quality.⁵ By enabling the FAIR principles for EOSC across scientific communities, stakeholder groups, and research outputs at a European, national, and institutional level, FAIR-IMPACT improved access to and management of FAIR research outputs and stimulated the development and uptake of a wide range of innovative services. By translating and implementing FAIR solutions across domains, the project also contributed to multi-disciplinary scientific cooperation. With its focus on increasing FAIRness, FAIR-IMPACT improved public trust in, and reproducibility of, science, transforming the way researchers share and exploit research outputs. The ultimate aim of this was to support better quality, validation, and higher research productivity.

This report details the sustainability planning for the 19 project outputs identified as important for EOSC and the global research community. These outputs are categorised as Key Exploitable Results (KER), Key Outputs (KO), and Key Functions (KF), representing a wide range of recommendations, guidelines, policies, best practices, frameworks, tools, and services.

1. **Key Exploitable Result (KER):** an identified main interesting result⁶ which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be made useful and derive benefits downstream in the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education.
2. **Key Output (KO):** other important project result not selected as a KER which requires sustainability measures during and after the project.
3. **Key Function (KF):** function performed by the project which requires sustainability measures during and after the project.

A summary of the outputs and their sustainability measures is listed in the table below. Whether maintained as static resources or carried forward by project partners and/or community stakeholders, these outputs will help shape policy development and best practices for a viable and FAIR EOSC.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057344>

² <http://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/831558>

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en

⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces/>

⁵ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-data-quality/#::~:~:text=The%20FAIR%20metrics%20and%20Data,and%20adopt%20tools%20as%20appropriate.>

⁶ According to the Horizon 2020 text, a result is defined as: "Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights".

Table 1 - Overview of outputs and sustainability approaches

Output category	Type of output	Name of output	Brief description	Sustainability plan
KER	FAIR Support	Persistent identifier support programme	A persistent identifier support programme and guidance for the provision of PID services in EOSC, including mechanisms and components to facilitate adoption and implementation of the EOSC PID Policy and alignment with PID practices.	Reports and event materials are published on Zenodo and a dedicated FAIR-IMPACT webpage. Relevant guides and recommendations are to be included in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliant Assessment Toolkit (CAT). The CAT and Knowledge Base will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. The German NFDI - an EOSC National Node, and their related PID working group PID4NFDI, are interested in adopting the PID policy related guidance of FAIR-IMPACT. The discussions are ongoing.
KER	FAIR Guidance	FAIR-IMPACT metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines	A comprehensive set of guidelines and recommendations for the governance, creation, mapping, sharing, reuse, FAIRness assessment, and interoperability of semantic artefacts within EOSC. These guidelines build on multiple WP4 deliverables.	Selected guidelines are presented in scientific publications to reach relevant communities and increase visibility. Some articles will be published after the end of the project. GitHub repositories have been created to allow continuous updates, discussions, and improvements by the community. The sustainability is reinforced through the involvement of project members, use cases, and external working groups, such as the new RDA FAIR Mappings WG or historical RDA Vocabulary Services IG. The long-term impact depends on the broader adoption of semantic artefacts and metadata within EOSC-related projects. The EOSC Federation Handbook points to the D4.4 "Guidelines for recommended metadata standard for research software within EOSC" as a reference document to comply with when describing Research Software.
KER	FAIR Support	FAIR assessment of software	The discipline-agnostic metrics for FAIR software assessment developed in the project and the implementation of some metrics into F-UJI.	UEDIN-SSI will sustain the discipline-agnostic metrics for research software, updating them when relevant. UBremen will support the software implementations in F-UJI through the GitHub repository. Community support to further develop these implementations is welcomed through the open source repository.

Output category	Type of output	Name of output	Brief description	Sustainability plan
KER	FAIR Guidance	Component and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within and across disciplines	Recommendations and guidelines for components and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic and technical interoperability in EOSC within and across disciplines.	Reports have been published on Zenodo and presented at relevant events, meetings and conferences with focus given to the future development of interoperability for the EOSC. Relevant EOSC-A Task Forces and Opportunity Areas have been of special interest. A summary of the recommendations will be sent to the editorial group of the EOSC Federated Handbook for possible incorporation in the next version.
KO	Project Instrument	Long-term preservation of project deliverables and data	Over 170 project outputs. These include deliverables and underlying data, milestone documents, intermediary results and intermediary data, code, reports and working documents.	All relevant project outputs were deposited in the Zenodo FAIR-IMPACT community. The main software outputs and technical recommendations were deposited into GitHub. At the end of the project selected assets (including all deliverables and milestones) will be deposited in the certified DANS Data Station repository for long-term preservation.
KO	Project Instrument	FAIR-IMPACT website	Project website with over 600 pieces of content and 3600+ registered users	The website will be maintained online after the end of the project as a static resource for five years after the end of the project. Trust-IT will ensure access to information on the website and maintain it with minimal technical effort.
KO	FAIR Support	FAIR Implementation Framework and catalogue of resources	The FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF) is a set of steps that helps different stakeholder groups to become more FAIR-enabling. One component of the framework is a catalogue of resources which aims to highlight existing tools, methods or approaches that can support the implementation of the FAIR Principles.	The catalogue was updated twice over the life of the project to include descriptions and links to tools, methods and approaches coming from the current INFRAEOSC projects. Trust-IT will maintain the catalogue portal for a period of 5 years after the project ends.
KO	FAIR Support	FAIR Implementation	Our FAIR Implementation workshop series was free and open to all. The workshops provided brief	The format of FAIR Implementation workshops will be continued for the European repository community via the FIDELIS project.

Output category	Type of output	Name of output	Brief description	Sustainability plan
		Workshop series materials	overviews of current and emerging tools, methods and approaches to producing, managing and sharing FAIR data at the organisational, data service provider, and national levels.	To allow others to consider adopting the format (e.g., INFRAEOSC projects such as EOSC Gravity), we developed a blueprint on planning and delivering the sessions. We promoted this blueprint via the Horizon Europe Communications and Engagement Working Group.
KO	FAIR Support	FAIR Implementation Stories	FAIR Implementation Stories were produced by all those supported through FAIR-IMPACT's open calls for financial and in-kind support. Those supported shared the lessons learned about implementing different tools, methods and approaches which can provide guidance and inspiration to help others to adopt or implement these tools and approaches.	We adapted the template produced by the FAIRsFAIR project to produce our FAIR Implementation Stories. Our stories have been added to the FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo collection under a CC-BY license to ensure that the outputs will be findable, accessible and reusable. We have linked the sets of FAIR Implementation Stories from the support actions to the relevant tools, methods or approaches to allow for discovery via the FIF catalogue as well as the project website and the project Zenodo collection.
KO	FAIR Guidance	Shared long-term vision of PID usage in EOSC	Documentation on PID usage and provision for service providers based on a collaborative effort.	The Opportunity Area-1: PIDs potential expansion to a supply-side would be the natural home for the guidelines on shared long-term vision of PID usage in EOSC. Discussion on the mandate of the OAs is ongoing to support a sustainable EOSC Federation. All three reports have an explicit focus on longevity and persistence and with the PID service providers as the main target groups. Relevant guides and recommendations are to be included in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliant Assessment Toolkit (CAT). The CAT and Knowledge Base will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. A podcast on the future prospects of PIDs and related EOSC PID coordination mechanisms for EOSC service providers has been published.
KO	FAIR Guidance	User-tailored guidelines for PIDs (policy and practice)	Documentation on PID implementation and minting practices for end users on managing different workflows, data types and research objects and guidelines on creating user-tailored and EOSC compliant PID policies for PID Managers.	User guidelines on best practices of PID usage published on the FAIR-IMPACT website as a stand-alone resource and on Zenodo as a full report. Guidelines outlined for PID Managers on creating a user-tailored and EOSC compliant PID policy. Both sets of recommendations are included in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit. The CAT and

Output category	Type of output	Name of output	Brief description	Sustainability plan
				Knowledge Base will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. The EOSC Federation Handbook points to the D3.3 “Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PDI Policy” as a reference document to comply with when citing data.
KO	FAIR Support	Semantic artefact catalogues and their connectors to data repositories	Multiple discipline-specific semantic artefact catalogues (SAC) the project contributed to. It also encompasses the connectors developed or experimented between semantic artefact catalogues and data repositories.	Each SAC involved in FAIR-IMPACT will be supported by its leading organisation beyond the project. The open-source connectors will be maintained by the teams/institutions that have developed them. These resources are often already established beyond research prototypes and backed by established research infrastructures. In certain cases, the adoption of OntoPortal SAC technology, –explicitly developed to be shared and sustained beyond project fundings– further ensures long-term support.
KO	FAIR Support	MOD and MOD-API	The vocabulary adopted by FAIR-IMPACT to semantically describe semantic artefacts and their catalogues, ensuring better FAIRness for SAs. MOD-API builds on MOD to specify a REST web service API for SACs, enabling seamless interoperability and unified access to SAs across platforms and domains.	The sustainability of MOD and MOD-API relies on establishing a long-term standardisation mechanism, in continuation with RDA and potentially within W3C, to maintain and evolve these specifications beyond FAIR-IMPACT. MOD has a strong foundation, having existed before the project and now being adopted as core metadata model inside the OntoPortal SAC technology, and documented on GitHub. By the project’s end, the MOD-API has been adopted by multiple SACs, ensuring better interoperability across underlying technologies. Even in the absence of evolution, MOD and MOD-API specifications will remain usable, serving as a foundation for future standardisation steps.
KO	FAIR Support	FAIR assessment of data	All discipline-agnostic and discipline-specific metrics for FAIR data assessment developed in the project, as well as the F-UJI and FAIR-Aware tools.	UBremen will sustain the GitHub implementation of all metrics and F-UJI. Metrics will be reviewed and updated when relevant. The open source GitHub repository allows community review and support of the tool for continuous improvement. KNAW-DANS will sustain FAIR-Aware.
KO	FAIR Guidance	Guidelines for transparency	Final guidelines and prototypes which support both enabling FAIR and assessing the FAIRness and	D5.3 will present all the final developments, lessons learnt, and next steps for the guidelines and prototypes. Work on this will be continued in the

Output category	Type of output	Name of output	Brief description	Sustainability plan
			trustworthiness of different types of digital objects in multiple domains.	EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects, as it supports the increased trustworthiness of repositories.
KF	FAIR Instrument	Synchronisation Force	A coordination mechanism to engage stakeholders responsible for implementing a FAIR EOSC, ensuring compliance with its rules of participation, alignment with the guidelines established by the EOSC governance bodies, and engagement from the user base.	A guidance document is available that can serve as a “blueprint” describing the objectives of the Synchronisation Force workshops, the stakeholders involved, the process, as well as the investment needed to run the workshop series. A one-day SF workshop module is designed that could be used to continue the work e.g. in the context of the EOSC Winter Schools.
KF	FAIR Instrument	EOSC FAIR Champions	FAIR-IMPACT established a group of 13 EOSC FAIR Champions that supported the project as ambassadors. The EOSC FAIR Champions have been engaged in many different ways in the project activities and recognise themselves as such.	Contact will be maintained with the Champions beyond the end of the project. The outputs produced by them will impact future reports, projects and FAIR implementation, continuation of knowledge on FAIR and their lessons learnt can serve future initiatives. Maintaining the current form is not important, but membership of such networks and the focus on a durable knowledge base are.
KF	FAIR Instrument	National Roadshows	Online or on-site events with the aim of speeding up FAIR adoption by communities in different European countries, thanks to the engagement with local facilitators.	The FAIR-IMPACT project published a “National Roadshow Blueprint document”, to provide suggestions and guidance on how to organise such a series of workshops. Information about resources needed to organise the series is added to this, to help quantify the investment.
KF	FAIR Instrument	Forum related to semantic artefacts, their catalogues, mappings and governance within EOSC	This corresponds to the forum-role played overall by FAIR-IMPACT to discuss semantics with (EOSC) communities. This includes semantic artefact catalogue advocacy and support for EOSC communities, the discussions related to mappings and governance or adoption of semantics and metadata in general.	Sustainability will rely on various RDA groups, including a new WG on FAIR mappings, and continued engagement from partners. The OntoPortal Alliance will partially take over support for communities adopting semantic artefact catalogues; initiatives like the annual OntoPortal Workshops or the OntoPortal federation both established during FAIR-IMPACT will contribute to long term support of this function.

1 Sustainability approach and lessons learned

The overall objective of FAIR-IMPACT was to realise an EOSC of FAIR data and services by supporting the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices across scientific communities and research outputs at a European, national, and institutional level. This directly supported the second general objective of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) to “*Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse, and combine results*” and contributed to the third objective to “*Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results*”.⁷ FAIR-IMPACT worked with the EOSC Association and its Task Forces⁸ and Opportunity Area Expert Groups⁹ to deliver its mission to translate viable solutions, guidelines, and frameworks developed for one domain, stakeholder group, or output type and support their application in others. In short, the project’s concentrated coordination with EOSC A and TFs means that its outputs will be sustained through the very structure of the EOSC itself.

The value of the coordination, alignment, and engagement delivered by the project is maximised if the results are sustainable and aligned with the SRIA objectives to avoid duplication and support promotion and wide adoption of the outputs of FAIR-IMPACT and other related projects and initiatives. Planning for the long-term sustainability of project outputs was woven into the activities of the work packages and coordinated by the dedicated Task 1.4 on sustainability. As such, various measures were developed throughout the project with sustainability in mind. Each work package identified key outputs using the EU designation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) as well as Key Outputs (KOs) and Key Functions (KFs) and detailed sustainability plans for their long-term viability.

1.1 Building on past achievements

Where appropriate the FAIR-IMPACT project built on the successful sustainability approach of its predecessor the FAIRsFAIR project.¹⁰ The philosophy behind this approach is that thinking about sustainability of all outputs from the very outset, in a structured manner, really helps to ensure that the outputs are maintained after the project. In practice this meant that the sustainability of the project outcomes needed to be woven throughout all work packages within the project. Sustainability measures taken in the project across the various work packages were described and continuously monitored as part of the inventory of project outputs.

Next to this, the FAIR-IMPACT project itself provided an opportunity to sustain, further develop, and promote results from FAIRsFAIR and other H2020 projects. Examples of this are

⁷ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>.

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces/>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

¹⁰ <https://fairfair.eu/project-management-and-sustainability>

the continuation of successful key functions developed in FAIRsFAIR: the Synchronisation Force, the National Roadshow series, as well as the concept of FAIR Champions.¹¹

Examples of important key outputs FAIR-IMPACT sustained and further developed and promoted amongst its stakeholder groups are the ACME-FAIR guide¹², as well as the F-UJI¹³ and FAIR-Aware¹⁴ tools for FAIR assessment. Similarly, with respect to semantic artefacts, FAIR-IMPACT has built on MOD (metadata vocabulary for SAS previously developed within RDA and discussed in FAIRsFAIR)¹⁵ to consolidate this effort and propose the MOD-API for interoperability of semantic artefact catalogues.

1.2 Inventory of project outputs and Key Impact Pathways

Following the example of the EU-funded FAIRsFAIR project, an internal inventory of project outputs was developed as a living document and a first step to plan and implement sustainability actions during the lifetime and immediate aftermath of the project. Key project outputs were assigned to one of three labels:

- **Key Exploitable Result (KER):** as originally defined in the Horizon 2020 context, an identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be made useful and derive benefits downstream in the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education.
- **Key Output (KO):** other important project result not selected as a KER which requires sustainability measures during and after the project.
- **Key Function (KF):** function performed by the project which requires sustainability measures during and after the project.

We also categorised our outputs in different types (Project instrument, FAIR instrument, FAIR guidance, and FAIR support) to more clearly indicate the purpose of each output. Figure 1 displays the classification of all outputs according to both these categorisations.

¹¹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/advisory-board/synchronisation-force> ,
<https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-national-roadshow-series> ,
<https://www.fairsfair.eu/advisory-board/egfc>

¹² <https://www.fairsfair.eu/acme-fair-guide-rpo>

¹³ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-ujj-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

¹⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>

¹⁵ <https://GitHub.com/FAIR-IMPACT/MOD>

Figure 1 - FAIR-IMPACT Output Types

Throughout the FAIR-IMPACT project, progress toward achieving the SRIA objectives was periodically assessed, enabling direct feedback to the EOSC Partnership on challenges to implementing policies and practices. Our Key Impact Pathways (see Figure 2) were aligned to the Horizon Europe approach for capturing and communicating impact. The FAIR-IMPACT contribution to achieving the draft UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science¹⁶ and Sustainable Development Goals¹⁷ was also established and is represented visually in the figure below. The expected outcomes of the project lead to four longer-term expected impacts that are defined in the Horizon Europe Work Programme.

¹⁶ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

¹⁷ <https://www.unesco.org/en/sdgs>

Figure 2 – FAIR-IMPACT Key Impact Pathways

1.3 Implementing sustainability plans for project outputs

In the context of implementing sustainability for the project outputs, three different sustainability levels were distinguished.

- The first level of sustainability was defined in the project's Data Management Plan, which provided that **project results were immediately made accessible, open and reusable**. This ensured that outputs could be widely used and adopted by the target communities.
- The second level of sustainability was to **actively engage** with and participate in the EOSC governance as well as its Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups **to make sure that outputs would feed into EOSC documents and recommendations**. This was achieved by direct and targeted contributions to the activities of the Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups and by providing extensive project feedback on the various document drafts produced by these groups.
- The third level of building sustainability was to **ensure that our outputs have a maximum impact on and are adopted by key stakeholders**.

Each work package was responsible for elaborating, planning, and implementing the necessary actions to ensure that the sustainability of the project outputs were appropriately considered and addressed. These sustainability measures were described and continuously monitored as part of the inventory of project outputs described in section 1.2. Planning for sustainability of each project output followed a set of key questions:

- What is the sustainability plan for the output/function?
- Who is involved in sustainability of the results?
- What are the sustainability actions already taken?
- What other sustainability actions are needed?
- Do other stakeholders depend on parts of the KER/KO/KF?
- How is the KER/KO/KF important in the EOSC and/or FAIR ecosystem as a whole?

The sustainability of the FAIR-IMPACT outputs is to a considerable extent dependent on their adoption by the project's consortium partners and stakeholders, by the EOSC governance and upcoming Federation of Nodes, as well as by other EOSC-related projects funded by the EC. The sustainability is also assisted by the adoption of project outputs by the wider European FAIR support and research community.

The promotion amongst stakeholder communities of project outputs, those of FAIR-IMPACT as well as of other projects and initiatives, was part of the Synchronisation Force activity. The

main recommendations from the Synchronisation Force activity regarding FAIR implementation in EOSC are communicated as a White Paper (D1.3).¹⁸

The project maintained open channels of communication with the EOSC Association, through interaction with relevant Task Forces and regular collaboration with the EOSC Focus project.¹⁹ The deliverables and outputs were disseminated as input to the work of the relevant EOSC Association Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups. The project actively participated in the EOSC Winter Schools 2024²⁰ and 2025,²¹ where input was provided during impact and sustainability sections of the programme. The project also participated in the EOSC Working Group on Impact and the regular EOSC Horizon Europe projects Coordination meetings organised by the EC.²²

In addition, project outputs were presented in several European countries and articulated in a national context as part of the FAIR-IMPACT Roadshow series²³ and included in different open calls for support²⁴ that boosted the adoption of different solutions, as well as internationally attended FAIR Implementation Workshops.²⁵

1.4 Challenges and opportunities for sustainable planning

The main overall objective of FAIR-IMPACT was to expand FAIR solutions across EOSC. The project worked towards this goal in a highly complex landscape with a multitude of stakeholders and an EOSC that had not yet found its final technical and organisational shape. The concept of the EOSC as a federation of nodes only arose during the second half of the lifetime of the project. By the time of writing, the only node in existence is the EOSC EU node, which limited the scope of advanced planning.

At the same time there was a strong belief that, based on the overall goal of the project, FAIR-IMPACT should directly contribute to the implementation of the EOSC. In order to achieve this, a certain level of validation from the EOSC structures was required to ensure the long-term sustainability and uptake by the different communities of the project outputs.

This is the first reason why the FAIR-IMPACT took the lead on the topic of project sustainability and the associated challenges in different EOSC-related contexts.

FAIR-IMPACT also realised that planning for the long-term sustainability of project outcomes in an ever-changing landscape is a common challenge for many EOSC-related projects. The exploitation of outputs after a project ends depends partly on their uptake and adoption by the various stakeholders of a project, yet there is currently no consensus on how to best

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/14979705>

¹⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/>

²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/other-fair-events/eosc-winter-school-2024>

²¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/articles-and-blogs/fair-impact-eosc-winter-school-2025-co-located-interoperability-workshop>

²² <https://eosc.eu/events/2024-coordination-meeting-of-eosc-related-projects-funded-under-horizon-europe/>

²³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows>

²⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-open-calls-support>

²⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

approach this. This was a second reason why the project decided to take the lead in this discussion.

In January 2024 FAIR-IMPACT discussed the challenges around the sustainability of project outputs at the Winter School, organised by the EOSC Association.

This was followed in June 2024 by the annual EOSC Horizon Europe projects Coordination meeting organised by the European Commission. At this event the sustainability discussion was continued in one of the breakout sessions and it was suggested by the EOSC-A Executive Board to organise a dedicated meeting with the stakeholders involved towards the end of the year.

This suggestion was picked up by FAIR-IMPACT. In December 2024 a meeting was held with representatives from seven EOSC-related projects, the EOSC-A secretariat as well as several members of the Executive Board of the EOSC Association.²⁶ The meeting provided an opportunity for the projects to articulate their sustainability challenges. The main recommendation from the side of the EOSC Association was to look at the emerging federation of nodes for the uptake of project outputs. However, for a number of projects this federation will not be there in time.

As another initiative, in September 2024 FAIR-IMPACT organised a sustainability session as part of its Synchronisation Force Workshop series 2024.²⁷ This topic was a new addition to the lineup for the Synchronisation Force that year. Given the shared nature of the topic and the associated challenges, it was decided to host a dedicated topical session to bring together different projects to discuss this together with some important stakeholders in the landscape. Around 40 participants joined the session to discuss the topic of sustainability. Short presentations were given by the FAIR-IMPACT Project Officer, the European Commission, and the EOSC-Association. These presentations discussed the different types of sustainability, the requirements and support mechanisms available towards sustainability, and next steps already on the radar to improve this.²⁸ The outcomes of this session are discussed in chapter 3 of this report.

Overall, the value of these initiatives to keep the broader discussion on project sustainability going within the EOSC context has been twofold. Awareness about the sustainability challenges of EOSC-related projects was raised amongst the key stakeholders. Secondly, it created opportunities for FAIR-IMPACT to have more specific discussions both with the editorial team of the EOSC Federation Handbook, as well as with one of the aspiring national nodes participating in the first wave of nodes, resulting in additional sustainability approaches.

²⁶ These projects were: FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-EASE, RDA-TIGER, RAISE, BlueCloud and SKILLS4EOSC.

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/14848907>

²⁸ Everhardt, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Horton, L., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., Rouchon, O., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). M1.9 Third Synchronisation Workshop Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848907>

2 Sustainability of project outputs

This section depicts the sustainability plans of each output at the moment of publishing this deliverable. As described above, the project outputs were categorised into the types KER, KO, and KF and are organised as such below.

2.1 Key Exploitable Results

2.1.1 Persistent Identifier Support Programme

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI”

L. Integrate widely used and adopted PIDs into institutional services and incentivize the use of PID technologies being developed for EOSC (Objectives 1 and 2).

What needs to be sustained

A guide on technical EOSC Persistent Identifier (PID) implementation based on the support programme on creating a EOSC compliant PID policy and other relevant PID guidance, created through a workshop addressing EOSC compliant PID implementations. This workshop demonstrated concrete tools, policies and developments within the realm of PIDs from the EOSC projects and used that to fuel further innovation through the FAIR-IMPACT Open Support Call in January 2024. The workshop further provided insight into how you can adapt existing PID implementation best practices and apply them to your domain and work. The recordings and materials of the workshop EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices²⁹ are available on Zenodo. A technical EOSC PID Implementation Guide & Program³⁰ is another output part of the PID support programme, which provides a hands-on framework for adopting PIDs in alignment with EOSC policies and core solutions presented in infographics. The report outlines clear, actionable steps for incorporating PIDs into existing workflows, organised across three levels: national initiatives, service providers and institutions.

Why it needs to be sustained

Supporting organisations with FAIR-compliant PID implementation is crucial. An ecosystem only works if everyone buys in and this KER brings people in and sets them up to succeed within the ecosystem. This type of support programme is important for EOSC, which the Multi-Annual Roadmap of EOSC also confirms.

How it is/will be sustained

²⁹ van Lieshout, N., van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2023). EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices. Webinar, 21 November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245076>

³⁰ van Lieshout, N., Ramezani, S., van Horik, R., Horton, L., Turner, D., Davidson, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Lager, L., & Nordling, J. (2025). MS3.8 Technical EOSC PID implementation guide & program. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14779609>

All reports including recommendations and guidelines on the implementation and usage of PIDs are published in the FAIR-IMPACT community in Zenodo. The guidelines for national initiatives, service providers and institutions have also been separately published on the FAIR-IMPACT website. Relevant guides and recommendations are to be included in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliant Assessment Toolkit (CAT). The CAT and Knowledge Base³¹ will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. The German NFDI³² as an emerging national EOSC Node and their related PID working group PID4NFDI³³ are interested in adopting the PID policy related guidance of FAIR-IMPACT. The discussions are currently ongoing.

2.1.2 Metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI”

- B. Accelerate the adoption of interoperability and semantic artefact catalogues (Objective 2).
- E. Use European and domain-specific semantic artefact catalogues in national infrastructures and guidelines aligned with European standards and vocabularies (Objective 2).
- F. Support adoption of general and domain-specific standards to increase adoption of FAIR practices and develop plans to facilitate reuse (Objective 2).
- H. Establish protocols for dealing with the cost of data management, data stewardship, maintenance, and preservation of research outputs (including software and semantic artefacts) and making them eligible within national funding schemes (Objective 1).
- I. Promote collaborations between national infrastructures and cross-border initiatives to promote consistent FAIR data standards and enhanced international interoperability (Objective 1).

What needs to be sustained

This KER consists of a comprehensive set of guidelines and recommendations for the governance, creation, mapping, sharing, reuse, FAIRness assessment, and interoperability of semantic artefacts (SAs) within EOSC. It corresponds to the KER4 in the original proposal. This includes means to produce and share FAIR semantic artefacts, enable harmonised and interoperable semantic artefact catalogues, crosswalks and mappings all of which to improve data interoperability within and across disciplines. Furthermore, the guidelines for Research

³¹ Knowledge Base available: <https://cat.argo.grnet.gr/pid-selection> Published reports: Hugo, W., Van de Sompel, H., & Hakala, J. (2025). The PID Landscape - a Technical View (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14881287> & Hugo, W., O'Neill, E., Heinmann, N., & Priddy, M. (2025). DataSet - PID Knowledge Base (1.3.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14868785>

³² <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

³³ <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>

Software MetaData (a.k.a RSMD guidelines)³⁴ is a community-developed set of recommendations for researchers to archive, reference, cite and describe software, ensuring a pathway towards FAIR software.

These guidelines build on multiple WP4 milestones and deliverables, covering aspects such as recommended metadata standards for research software, FAIR-by-design SA methodology, FAIRness assessment for SAs, governance models for SAs, FAIR mappings, and lifecycle management of semantic artefacts thru interoperable SA catalogues.

Why it needs to be sustained

Any data stakeholders dealing with metadata and ontologies are directly concerned with the KER. In essence, it is the first set of EOSC recommendations and guidelines focusing on FAIR semantic artefacts and research software.

The KER represents outcomes of FAIR-IMPACT specifically targeting multiple objectives or requirements discussed in the EOSC SRIA. For example:

- *SRIA: To date an overarching, coordinated approach to metadata and ontologies for scholarly resources has for the most part been missing. ⇒ By the end of FAIR-IMPACT, this statement shall still be true "overall" but shall be partially addressed for some communities and/or disciplines such as the ones involved in FAIR-IMPACT.*
- *SRIA: Work on developing, improving and applying metadata schemas and ontologies – both for specific disciplines and for general use – is happening in many different places, but is often not well-coordinated. ⇒ Addressed at disciplines level within FAIR-IMPACT. The project created the environment for communities and/or disciplines to coordinate and exchange one another.*
- *SRIA: Develop EOSC guidelines for a minimum metadata description based on existing metadata schemas and tools to allow data discovery and metadata exchange across federated repositories and scientific communities. ⇒ Partially addressed for: (i) research software for which the RSMD guidelines are now available; (ii) semantic artefact for which FAIR-IMPACT consolidated and completed FAIRsFAIR previous work with MOD; (iii) mappings for which FAIR-IMPACT described FAIR mappings recommendations and supported the new SSSOM metadata model developed aside.*
- *SRIA: Develop governance structures for coordinating the work on metadata and ontologies within EOSC, both for specific disciplinary communities and for overall coordination. ⇒ Well addressed during FAIR-IMPACT: (i) Semantic artefact governance models studied by disciplinary approaches by reviewing and analysing semantic artefact community practices and governance approaches. (ii) Early discussion within groups like the OntoPortal Alliance for an overall coordination and governance of multiple semantic artefact catalogues. Overall coordination of SAC providers in the context of the MOD-API implementation action.*

³⁴ <https://GitHub.com/FAIR-IMPACT/RSMD-guidelines>

The KER represents outcomes of FAIR-IMPACT specifically targeting multiple aspects discussed in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF). This will be detailed in the justification of the KO on SAC and their connectors (Section 2.2.8).

How it is/will be sustained

The sustainability strategy for these sets of guidelines and recommendations ensures long-term availability, visibility, and adoption with different approaches detailed hereafter. Every author of the written documentation or their corresponding institution is involved in the sustainability of the results.

- Scientific dissemination: Selected guidelines are presented in scientific publications to reach relevant communities and increase visibility.³⁵ Some scientific publications are being written at the end of the project and shortly after.
- Community engagement: GitHub repositories have been created to allow continuous updates, discussions, and improvements by the community.³⁶
- New working group: The sustainability is reinforced through the involvement of project members, use cases, and external working groups, such as:
 - The new RDA Working Group on FAIR Mappings: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg>
 - The historical RDA Vocabulary and Semantic Services Interest Group (VSSIG): <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/vocabulary-services-interest-group>
 - The OntoPortal Alliance: <https://ontoportal.org/>
- Ongoing adoption in EOSC: The long-term impact depends on the broader adoption of semantic artefacts and metadata within EOSC-related projects. The KER sustainability will be assured in the long term by a broader adoption of semantics, ontology and metadata in EOSC related projects and the adoption of the RSMD guidelines by EOSC partners and European academic institutions. The adoption of the RSMD guidelines in the EOSC handbook is a clear intent to support software as a first-class research output. In other words, encouraging projects and activities around EOSC to adopt semantics will directly sustain, and if necessary revise and update the metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines. Within EOSC there currently are no new funded initiatives fully dedicated to an EOSC strategy for the deployment of semantic artefacts despite the recent attention on semantic interoperability and metadata and ontologies in EOSC governance and EOSC scientific communities.

³⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4>, <https://hal.science/hal-04678381v1>, <https://hal.science/hal-04106533>, <https://hal.science/hal-04094847/>, <https://hal.science/hal-04088537v2>, <https://hal.science/hal-04207343>, <https://hal.science/hal-04312604>, <https://agbeltran.GitHub.io/publication/2024-07-15-FOAM-FAIRmappings>

³⁶ <https://GitHub.com/FAIR-IMPACT>

2.1.3 FAIR assessment of software

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the update of AI”

F. Support adoption of general and domain-specific standards to increase adoption of FAIR practices and develop plans to facilitate reuse (Objective 2).

What needs to be sustained

With regards to the FAIR assessment of software, FAIR-IMPACT produced metrics and adapted a tool to implement practical tests. Based on the FAIR4RS principles, FAIR-IMPACT produced the first set of metrics for the FAIR assessment of software, including both discipline-agnostic as well as a set of discipline-specific (social sciences) metrics.³⁷ Some of the metrics have also been implemented in a new version of the F-UJI tool, initially designed to only assess data, as a proof of concept to make the automated FAIR assessment of software possible.³⁸ Both the generic and discipline-specific metrics and the current implementation in F-UJI are part of the sustainability plan.

Why it needs to be sustained

The creation of the metrics for software and their implementation in the automated assessment tool F-UJI makes it possible for the first time to (automatically) assess the FAIRness of software, and subsequently improve it. This is an important step towards the increase of FAIR digital objects in EOSC and the ecosystem as a whole, and helps emphasise the importance of FAIR software. The metrics provide an important implementation of the FAIR4RS Principles that allow assessment, and more explorations on the best methods and practices for such assessment will continue to be explored in the future.

The primary audience of this work are developers of research software. The KER also has different secondary stakeholders: repositories storing/archiving research software; funders of software; RPOs developing/supporting research software in some way; infrastructures creating a right environment for research software to be and remain FAIR over time.

How it is/will be sustained

UEDIN-SSI will commit to sustaining the metrics for software in conjunction with their role in the EVERSE project.³⁹ This includes maintaining the accessibility and findability of the metrics, and reviewing and updating them according to developments in the field. The discipline-specific metrics for the CEESDA community will not be explicitly sustained beyond

³⁷ Chue Hong, N., Breitmoser, E., Antonioletti, M., Davidson, J., Garijo, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gruenpeter, M., Huber, R., Jonquet, C., Priddy, M., Shepherdson, J., Verburg, M., & Wood, C. (2023). D5.2 - Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

³⁸ Moraw, K., Antonioletti, M., Breitmoser, E., Chue Hong, N., & Priddy, M. (2024). M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890043>

³⁹ <https://everse.software/>

FAIR-IMPACT. They were created as an example of possible metrics extension, and open for CEESDA to use and sustain on their own, but no formal sustainability plan has been agreed on as it is currently not deemed to be the most efficient use of resources and effort. The implementation of some of the metrics into F-UJI as practical tests will be supported by UBremen in the F-UJI GitHub repository. However, further development is not currently part of this plan. Some of the results of the FAIR-IMPACT Support Action⁴⁰ indicated interest by other groups to continue the F-UJI implementation of additional metrics, but no concrete plans have been agreed on. The GitHub repository is open source and welcomes contributors looking to advance the work. Successful further implementation would require a developer and open source coordinator to engage interested parties in implementation, contributions, and maintenance. UPM has expressed interest in continuing this activity after the project lifetime. No formal commitments are documented, but there is direct communication to ensure the activity is well taken care of.

2.1.4 Component and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within and across disciplines

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objectives and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the update of AI”

B. Accelerate the adoption of interoperability and semantic artefact catalogues. Support AI-enabled services, engaging discipline-specific groups that facilitate interoperability and reuse more automatically through automatic annotation, data linkage, data homogenisation, data transformation, or other similar approaches, including global alignment (Objective 2).

Strategic Pillar 3 “Ensuring research security and sovereignty”

C. Define a harmonised operational (including cybersecurity aspects) and legal framework facilitate the secure sharing and governance of, and access to, data (including sensitive data) and services. (Objectives 2 and 3).

D. Encourage the development and coordination of national data sovereignty frameworks that align with European and international research initiatives (Objective 2).

What needs to be sustained

Interoperability for data, software and all other research output is a cornerstone for an EOSC, which provides value for research and researchers within and across scientific and institutional domains as well as across geographical borders.

The FAIR-IMPACT project has formulated guidelines and recommendations to support and enhance legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability based on surveys, desktop analysis, engagement with key stakeholders (in the form of interviews and/or

⁴⁰ Assessing and improving existing research software using a new extension of F-UJI
<https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-assessment-and-improvement-research-software>

workshops) from EOSC-projects, EU initiatives and international organisations, as well as tests of EOSC components.

Why it needs to be sustained

These guidelines and recommendations need to be sustained to the benefit of the future development of the EOSC at all levels from high level strategy development and updates to implementations, development of components and research practices.

How it is/will be sustained

The guidelines and recommendations are presented in project deliverables, which are all published in the FAIR-IMPACT Community on Zenodo. Several project partners are members of relevant groups and it is expected that these guidelines and recommendations will be part of the knowledge base feeding into:

- EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force⁴¹
- Opportunity Area 2: Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability⁴²
- RDA FAIR Mappings Working Group⁴³

Several project partners are members of the aforementioned Task Force and/or Opportunity Area Expert Group.

For Task Forces, Opportunity Areas and RDA WGs, before the end of the project we will provide a targeted summary of guidelines and recommendations for our partners to bring forward in these settings in a way which makes them easily suited to be adopted.

The first version of the EOSC Federated Handbook covering 2025-2026 was published in March 2025.⁴⁴ This KER of guidelines and recommendations supporting the implementation of legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability can feed into the second version of the Federated Handbook. A summary of the guidelines and recommendations is sent to the editorial group of the Handbook, with the suggestion of incorporation in the next version that is expected to appear in October 2025.

2.2 Key Outputs

2.2.1 Long-term preservation of project deliverables and data

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

The total package of deliverables and milestones from the FAIR-IMPACT project is broad and diverse and can therefore be mapped against all SRIA objectives.

⁴¹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/>

⁴² <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa2-metadata-ontologies-and-interoperability/>

⁴³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/activity/>

⁴⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/> : <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

What needs to be sustained

The FAIR-IMPACT project generated considerable documentation (over 170 project outputs).⁴⁵ These include deliverables and underlying data, milestone documents, intermediary results and intermediary data, code, reports and working documents. In particular, documentation that supported the KERs, KOs and KFs has been preserved to provide background and supporting information to the key project outputs. Work package leaders undertook to prepare and deposit the outputs in Zenodo. The dissemination and exploitation activities with regard to the project deliverables and data were guided by the FAIR-IMPACT Communication, Marketing & Engagement Plan.⁴⁶

Why it needs to be sustained

In 2023, the EU spent 381 billion euro on research and development.⁴⁷ This R&D often results in data which are useful for further and future research. If these data are not FAIR, they cannot be found, be accessed, do not interoperate and are therefore unfit to be reused. This would result in a huge financial loss for global research as well as a setback to scientific progress. Looking towards a future in which the adoption of machine learning and AI is becoming ubiquitous, FAIR data will play a crucial role in AI creating a foundation for trust and success.⁴⁸

Because of the above, the FAIR-IMPACT policies, guidelines, recommendations, support materials and tools are expected to remain highly relevant for a considerable time after the project ends.

How it is/will be sustained

Work Package and Task Leaders were responsible for depositing the outputs in Zenodo as they became available. The Zenodo deposits were organised using a FAIR-IMPACT community. This ensures that all materials are linked and easily findable. The FAIR-IMPACT community will not be added to after the end of the project, but could be linked to ongoing FAIR-related communities.

The main software outputs were deposited into GitHub.⁴⁹ Releases created in GitHub were added to the FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo community. Outputs are deposited under the CC-BY 4.0 (Attribution 4.0 International) licence, or MIT licence (code), and using recommended file formats.

⁴⁵ Source: FAIR-IMPACT community on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact>

⁴⁶ Pittonet, S., Davidson, J., Meneses, R., Mari, M., O'Connor, R., Nordling, J., Aubin, S., Kalaitzi, V., Grootveld, M., Turner, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Horton, L., Whyte, A., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Mejias, G., & Dillo, I. (2024). D7.1 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10785484>

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=R%26D_expenditure#:~:text=In%202023%2C%20

⁴⁸ <https://www.copyright.com/blog/unlocking-the-power-of-fair-data-building-trust-and-success-in-the-ai-era/>

⁴⁹ <https://GitHub.com/FAIR-IMPACT>

At the end of the project the selected assets will be deposited in the CoreTrustSeal certified trustworthy Data Station repository at DANS for long-term preservation. This ensures that all documentation has Dublin Core metadata. In the repository each dataset has a unique and persistent identifier. Selected software artefacts will be preserved using the Save Code Now⁵⁰ feature provided by Software Heritage (INRIA).⁵¹

2.2.2 FAIR-IMPACT website

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

The website is relevant as the first entry point to the many different assets developed by the project, and therefore it can be mapped against all SRIA objectives mapped by the other project outputs.

What needs to be sustained

The <https://fair-impact.eu> website has been online since summer 2022, seeing more than 20k users, almost 56k sessions and 136k views by the end of March 2025. Furthermore, the FAIR-IMPACT website has 3616 registered users (by March 2025), and this number will increase by the end of the project. The website has more than 600 piece of content published, including informative web pages (about the project activities and results, the open calls, the consortium and the expert boards, etc...), event pages and webforms for user registrations, use case and implementation story pages, news items, articles and blogs and media kit materials. The web pages also sign-post deliverables, milestones and other types of reports from Zenodo in an automatic way via APIs, thus facilitating users in searching and retrieving topic-related materials from Zenodo. All this information architecture is important and needs to be sustained at least for 5 years after the project conclusion.

Why it needs to be sustained

Maintaining the FAIR-IMPACT website pages live and ensuring a clear access to all the project outputs is important to ensure uptake and smooth access to the results after the project ends. It is also relevant as it represents the official community database for the FAIR-IMPACT community of 3616 registered users (March 2025), who can be invited to any other follow-up initiative taking on the legacy of the project.

How it is/will be sustained

The FAIR-IMPACT website will be available online for 5 years after the end of the project. Trust-IT Services will ensure access to information on the website, hosting and maintenance of the website on Trust-IT servers. The website will be maintained with minimal technical effort.

⁵⁰ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/save/> (accessed 10/02/2022).

⁵¹

<https://www.softwareheritage.org/2019/08/05/saving-and-referencing-research-software-in-software-heritage/> (accessed 10/02/2022).

Focusing on the management of personal data, KNAW-DANS, as a data controller, will keep defining the purposes for which and the means by which personal data is processed. Trust-IT Services, as a data processor, will process personal data only on behalf of the controller. Credentials to access and manage the platform could be given to a few individuals from the partner organisations, as joint controllers, in view of willing to dedicate effort in maintaining it, or to others indicated by the EC.

That said, the website serves as an entry point to the key deliverables, documents, guidelines and tools which are all sign-posted from open access repositories such as Zenodo and Github. Zenodo APIs have been constantly used to sign-post content pieces in two webpages for “Deliverables and milestones”⁵² and “publications and other materials”⁵³. The software collected in the Github FAIR-IMPACT organisation⁵⁴ is linked to the relevant webpages, including the About page⁵⁵. In the final revamp of the website information architecture and homepage, direct links to the Zenodo and GitHub communities will also be prominently showcased.

2.2.3 FAIR Implementation Framework and catalogue of resources

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

By helping to promote useful resources to data stewards, this KO addresses many different objectives and implementations. The output itself maps best to the Strategic and Operational Objective ‘SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design’.

What needs to be sustained

The FAIR Implementation Framework⁵⁶ is a set of steps that helps different stakeholder groups to become more FAIR-enabling. One component of the framework is a catalogue of resources⁵⁷ which aims to highlight existing tools, methods or approaches that can support the implementation of the FAIR Principles. We aimed in particular to promote those resources that were developed by other INFRAEOSC projects.

The FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF) catalogue of resources is made available as a stand-alone website linked to the main FAIR-IMPACT website. Both the stand-alone and main websites are provided and managed by Trust-IT, and a single-sign-on is active among the two websites, with editing rights allowed to a few FAIR-IMPACT partners working in adoption tasks. As per the main fair-impact.eu website, the FIF catalogue will also be available online for 5 years after the end of the project, with direct link from the main FAIR-IMPACT website, with KNAW-DANS that will remain data controller and Trust-IT main

⁵² <https://fair-impact.eu/deliverables-milestones>

⁵³ <https://fair-impact.eu/publications>

⁵⁴ <https://github.com/fair-impact>

⁵⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-expanding-fair-solutions-across-eosc>

⁵⁶ FAIR Implementation Framework <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

⁵⁷ FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

host and data processor for the upcoming 5 years. The website will be maintained with minimal technical effort. Credentials to access and manage the platform could be given to other individuals indicated by the EC. All resources linked via the catalogue are hosted in third party websites / repositories. The data in the catalogue can be migrated to any third party / project interested in maintaining such a catalogue after 2025 or moved to a long term repository, or turned into a GitHub object (but effort needs to be quantified, first). A snapshot of the resources included in the catalogue will be included in D2.2 Final iteration of the FAIR implementation framework.

Why it needs to be sustained

The catalogue provides a means of making the FAIR-enabling tools and resources mainly from the INFRAEOSC projects more visible to end users.

How it is/will be sustained

The main legacy of the FIF relates to the relevance of the identified FAIR enabling resources from the INFRAEOSC projects, which are all hosted by third party entities or on Zenodo, GitHub or other Open Access repositories, thus ensuring long term accessibility. The FIF Catalogue of Resources has also been added as a collection to FAIRsharing to increase visibility.⁵⁸ As we developed the first iteration of the FIF catalogue, we aligned elements of our metadata with that of the EOSC Marketplace, live at that time, to support longer term sustainability of the descriptions. In light of the move from the EOSC Marketplace to the EOSC EU Node, launched in late April 2024, we will consider the potential of adding the entire catalogue to the Resource Hub offered by the EOSC EU Node, while the individual resources should be individually included in the catalogue. As a bare minimum, the snapshot of the catalogue and the list of the resources there are included in an Annex to D2.2 which will be uploaded to Zenodo at the end of the project.

As we continue to refine and curate the catalogue, we will adopt the recommendations coming from WP4 in relation to good practice for making semantic artefacts more FAIR (e.g., the emerging SSSOM approach) and we anticipate that this will support the longer term availability and reusability of the knowledge contained within the catalogue in the event that the FIF website is no longer maintained.

The catalogue was updated twice over the life of the project to include emerging tools, methods and approaches coming from the current and future tranches of Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC projects.

The catalogue interface allows anyone to submit a candidate resource so in theory the catalogue can be extended without FAIR-IMPACT. However, we will need to consider who would approve submitted resources beyond the life of FAIR-IMPACT. There may be potential to identify a small group of volunteers from within FAIR-IMPACT and externally. If this is agreed, the catalogue can be extended to include new resources that are emerging through these projects. However, a collection policy will need to be developed to make clear what resources should be included and mechanisms for reviewing candidate resources for

⁵⁸FAIRsharing.org: FIF Catalogue of Resources; FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources, FAIRsharing ID: <https://fairsharing.org/6364>

inclusion will need to be resourced. This could be through new funded projects agreeing to take on this role or on a volunteer basis.

2.2.4 FAIR Implementation Workshop series materials

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 3 “Ensuring research security and sovereignty”

I. Define and implement training and procedures to develop information security management skills, especially those related to managing sensitive data in accordance with national and, where appropriate, European procedures (Objective 1).

J. Encourage the creation of institutional strategies and training programmes for data risk management aligned with European research security standards (Objectives 1 and 2).

What needs to be sustained

Our FAIR Implementation workshop series shared current and emerging tools, methods and approaches to producing, managing and sharing FAIR data at the organisational, data service provider, and national levels. The format of the FAIR Implementation Workshops was designed specifically to provide concise and practically focused introductions to current and emerging methods and approaches. FAIR-IMPACT has provided a blueprint⁵⁹ on how to deliver FAIR Implementation workshops so that other support initiatives can continue the series. We have also provided access to the recordings and slides that can be reused directly by researchers or indirectly by data stewards to support implementation of different tools, methods and approaches. Where relevant, recordings are also linked to resources described in the FIF catalogue as an additional source of guidance.

Why it needs to be sustained

By offering the series virtually, keeping within a 1-2 hour duration, and ensuring that recordings were provided, we aimed to reduce barriers to potential participants. The format of delivery has proven popular with up to 300 registrants signing up for each virtual workshop and many people joining more than one workshop. Sustaining the workshop materials helps to provide an easy entry point to support uptake of different tools and approaches. The continuation of the event series could help to ensure that new approaches and tools are shared as they emerge through ongoing and future INFRAEOSC projects.

How it is/will be sustained

Recordings of the workshops are freely available from the FAIR-IMPACT website. The recordings are also made available in the FAIR-IMPACT YouTube channel, with a related metadata description deposited in Zenodo. A link to the video on the FAIR-IMPACT YouTube channel is included in the metadata record. If applicable, the recording will be linked to the

⁵⁹ Davidson, J. (2025). Blueprint for planning and delivering FAIR Implementation Workshops. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102683>

related resource in the FIF catalogue of resources to provide support to potential implementers/adopters.

Efforts will be needed to ensure that the FAIR-IMPACT YouTube channel and the workshops recordings remain accessible. Work is ongoing to develop a YouTube playlist to provide access to the subset of workshop recordings.

The blueprint on how to deliver FAIR Implementation workshops will enable other support initiatives to continue the series. In addition, FAIR-IMPACT's Pathway to Impact white paper⁶⁰ provides a summary of lessons learned through the delivery of FAIR Implementation Workshop series that will be of value to anyone considering running such events.

2.2.5 FAIR Implementation Stories

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

FAIR Implementation Stories were produced by all those supported through FAIR-IMPACT's open calls for financial and in-kind support, which allows mapping to many different objectives and implementations. The output itself maps best to the Strategic and Operational Objective 'SO4 Increasing amounts of research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are FAIR by design'.

What needs to be sustained

The collection of Implementation Stories should remain accessible. In addition, FAIR-IMPACT's Pathway to Impact white paper⁶¹ provides a summary of lessons learned through the co-creation of FAIR Implementation Stories that will be of value to anyone considering to continue with this approach⁶².

Why it needs to be sustained

FAIR Implementation stories illustrate good practices and approaches to steps taken by research communities and organisations to support the implementation of the FAIR principles.

The creation of FAIR Implementation Stories is a condition of Route 1 and Route 2 support. To this end, the availability of the collection of stories also serves as a means of verifying the successful completion of those participating in FAIR-IMPACT support activities.

How it is/will be sustained

We have reused the template produced by the FAIRsFAIR project to produce our FAIR Implementation stories. By the end of the project, the collection of stories will have been added to the FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo community under a CC-BY licence to ensure that the outputs will be findable, accessible and reusable.

⁶⁰ Davidson, J., Newbold, E., Verburg, M., Thorpe, D. E., Linés, C., & Mari, M. (2025). D7.2 - FAIR adoption pathway white paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210109>

⁶¹ ibid

⁶² Davidson, J., & Kalaitzi, V. (2025). M2.9 FAIR implementation action plans ready (gamma) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15311010>

To improve the findability of specific stories, FAIR-IMPACT has provided browsing facets via the website⁶³ to enable future users to search for stories relating to a specific support action and/or tool. Where relevant, tools, solutions or approaches that were offered via our open calls are described in our FAIR Implementation Framework catalogue of resources. FAIR Implementation Stories are also linked to the relevant tool, method or approach in the catalogue to support findability via another route.

2.2.6 Shared long-term vision of PID usage in EOSC

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 2 "Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI"

I. Promote collaborations between national infrastructures and cross-border initiatives to promote consistent FAIR data standards and enhanced international interoperability (Objective 1).

L. Integrate widely used and adopted PIDs into institutional services and incentivize the use of PID technologies being developed for EOSC (Objectives 1 and 2).

What needs to be sustained

The idea put forward with this long-term vision⁶⁴ is to create a coordination mechanism between EOSC and PID service providers⁶⁵ to align their efforts and channel their needs on PID implementations within EOSC. The long-term vision is further based on a joint value proposition for PIDs.⁶⁶

Why it needs to be sustained

This KO helps to better understand the existing PID infrastructure and potential integration benefits across EOSC. The shared value proposition by PID providers was developed in alignment with the EOSC PID policy and it emphasises the roles of key actors, including PID Authorities, Service Providers, Managers, Owners, and End Users. By aligning these roles with existing infrastructures, the piece of work highlights the vital role of persistent identifiers in ensuring seamless operation of EOSC.

The long-term vision highlights the diverse benefits of PIDs across the research ecosystem. A major strength of the value proposition is its recognition of community governance. Many PID services are community-driven, ensuring long-term sustainability and alignment with Open Science principles. This model enhances the resilience and longevity of PID infrastructures, crucial for preserving research outputs over time.

⁶³ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

⁶⁴ Mejias, G., Nordling, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Lager, L., van Lieshout, N., & Newbold, E. (2025). D3.1 - Shared long-term vision for PID service providers on PID usage in EOSC (V1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112835>

⁶⁵ Mejias, G., Cousijn, H., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Nordling, J., van Lieshout, N., & Gonzalez-Beltran, A. (2023). M3.2 - Proposal for an EOSC PID Service providers coordination mechanism. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8405818>

⁶⁶ Mejias, G., Cousijn, H., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., van Lieshout, N., Tatum, C., & Lambert, S. (2023). M3.1 - Joint value proposition by relevant PID providers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7798215>

How it is/will be sustained

Relevant guides and recommendations are to be included in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliant Assessment Toolkit (CAT). The CAT and Knowledge Base will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. The German NFDI - an EOSC National Node, and their related PID working group PID4NFDI, are interested in adopting the PID policy related guidance of FAIR-IMPACT. The discussions are ongoing. All reports have been published in the FAIR-IMPACT community in Zenodo.

2.2.7 User-tailored guidelines for PIDs (policy and practice)

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI”

L. Integrate widely used and adopted PIDs into institutional services and incentivize the use of PID technologies being developed for EOSC (Objectives 1 and 2).

What needs to be sustained

Guidelines for PID Managers for creating user-friendly and EOSC compliant PID policies.⁶⁷ The work is a result of a collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project in which a Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) is being developed, to support PID Managers and others with services to encode, record, and query compliance with the policy. The EOSC PID policy is, as a case study, analysed with the CAT. The results provided by the report are relevant for all actors in the PID Ecosystem, such as PID Service Providers, PID Owners, PID Authorities and PID Standards Bodies. The main target group, however, are PID Managers, who have the responsibility to maintain the integrity of the relationship between entities and their PIDs. Furthermore, recommendations for end users on best practices on PID usage,⁶⁸ as defined by seven integrated use case partners representing various scientific domains, have been published on Zenodo and the end user recommendations will be published on the FAIR-IMPACT website as a stand-alone resource.

Why it needs to be sustained

There is a lack of standardised cross-domain guidance and widely accepted best practices for PID usage aimed particularly at end users. This report aims to bridge this gap by offering clear, adaptable, and applicable recommendations across multiple scientific fields. These guidelines will promote broad adoption and compliance with FAIR principles while ensuring end-user needs are met in the development of EOSC PID solutions. A more consistent PID implementation and precise data citation will enhance data quality. Clear best practices will also encourage targeted PID use, preventing zombie identifiers, maintaining trust in PID services, and controlling costs. The CAT service (aimed at assessing PID policies and developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC) is an important instrument to support the improvement of

⁶⁷ van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2024). D3.3 - Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PID Policy (V2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14092489>

⁶⁸ Nordling, J., Ramezani, P., Granger, S., L'Hours, H., Parkes, O., Juty, N., Newbold, E., Caminha Juaçaba Neto, R., Sennesal, F.-X., van Lieshout, N., & Lager, L. (2025). D3.2 - User guidelines on EOSC PID implementation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15081434>

PID policies. In other words, future availability of the CAT is needed to maintain user-tailored guidelines for PID policies.

How it is/will be sustained

The guidelines for PID Managers on creating user-friendly EOSC PID Policy compliant PID policies have been included as a recommended document for the Nodes to follow in the EOSC Federation Handbook (annex 2). These are also published on the FAIR-IMPACT website.⁶⁹

Discussions with the German NFDI - an aspiring EOSC National Node, and their related PID working group PID4NFDI, are interested in adopting the PID policy related guidance of FAIR-IMPACT. The discussions are ongoing. The most relevant of the in total 38 recommendations will be incorporated in the Knowledge Base instance for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT). The CAT will be deployed as a service in the newly confirmed EUDAT EOSC Node as an operational service. All reports have been published in the FAIR-IMPACT community in Zenodo. The guidelines for PID Managers are also published on the FAIR-IMPACT website.⁷⁰ The EOSC Federation Handbook points to the D3.3 “Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC Compliant PDI Policy” as a reference document to comply with when citing data.

2.2.8 Semantic artefact catalogues and their connectors to data repositories

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

See KER Metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines (Section 2.1.2).

What needs to be sustained

This KO encompasses the multiple discipline specific semantic artefact catalogues the project contributed to. This includes the catalogues pre-existing FAIR-IMPACT and developed and enhanced within the project, as well as the catalogues started during FAIR-IMPACT. It also encompasses the connectors developed or experimented between semantic artefact catalogues and data repositories.

FAIR-IMPACT collaborated with nine different use cases across various domains such as social sciences, astronomy, earth sciences, life science, and agronomy to demonstrate the impact of FAIR SAs on data repositories and (meta)data catalogues. Each use case has focused on the development and testing of software connectors to enable the use of controlled vocabularies for data annotation and indexing documentation. Whenever feasible the connectors were designed to be generalisable to either the underlying SAC technology (mostly OntoPortal) or the underlying data repository technology (such as Dataverse, GeoNetwork, OpenSILEX or DSpace). These efforts highlighted reproducible connection processes and measurable impacts of SA integration on improving (meta)data FAIRness. The use cases have produced fully described and operational connectors. The connectors between the catalogues and data repositories are (or will be) open source and their codes

⁶⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/technical-eosc-pid-implementation-guide-program>

⁷⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/guidelines-creating-user-tailored-eosc-compliant-pid-policy>

are shared on GitHub (see D4.6 (Use case driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories)⁷¹ for details).

Why it needs to be sustained

The growing proliferation of SAs brings new challenges, including their description, selection, evaluation, trustworthiness and interconnection. The landscape remains fragmented, with SAs distributed across various registries, collections, indexes, etc., presented in different formats, varying in size and structure, and often overlapping their domain coverage. Collecting and centralising SAs in the same platform represents another step to facilitate data interoperability by enhancing their organisation, discoverability and accessibility. SACs are essential tools for the identification, description, evaluation, and exchange of semantic artefacts, enhancing their reuse and alignment. SACs represent a cornerstone of a successful and effective process for sharing SAs and have to be considered as key elements in the SA lifecycle and for making SAs FAIR.

Multiple data stakeholders concerned about FAIR data are directly depending on accessing and leveraging semantic artefacts in their disciplines. Thus data stakeholders in agri-food, ecology/biodiversity, earth sciences and astronomy might directly be impacted by the discontinuation of the FAIR-IMPACT semantic artefact catalogues.

SAs and their Catalogues are explicitly highlighted in the EOSC SRIA and MAR (see KER section 2.1.2). Semantic artefact catalogues were the focus of the 2nd theme of the EOSC Task Force on semantic interoperability. The EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) further supports this vision by providing a set of guidelines on technical and semantic interoperability, enabling communities to overcome silos and foster collaboration and reuse. Among the key components identified by the EOSC-IF are SAs and their catalogues.

Furthermore, sustaining the connectors beyond FAIR-IMPACT is crucial to ensure the continued interoperability between SACs and (meta)data repositories, enabling FAIR research data. By standardising how repositories integrate and use FAIR semantic artefacts, these connectors enhance data findability, interoperability, and reusability across diverse scientific domains and infrastructures. Without long-term support, the risk of fragmentation, duplicated efforts, and reduced accessibility to standardised vocabularies increases, ultimately hindering the adoption of FAIR principles in research data management. Thus anyone depositing and searching datasets in connected data repositories would also be impacted by the discontinuation of connectors.

How it is/will be sustained

The sustainability of this KO relies on a mix of research and infrastructure funding and support to maintain semantic artefact catalogues and their connectors beyond the project. Each SAC involved in FAIR-IMPACT will be supported by its leading organisation beyond the project:

- AgroPortal pre-dates FAIR-IMPACT. It is to be maintained/sustained by INRAE (MISTEA research unit and DipSO);

⁷¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14917164>

- EcoPortal pre-exists FAIR-IMPACT. It is to be maintained/sustained by LifeWatch ERIC;
- EarthPortal was developed during FAIR-IMPACT and is to be maintained/sustained by CNRS / Data Terra;
- OntoPortal-Astro was prototyped during FAIR-IMPACT. It is to be finished and consolidated in the context of the OPAL project (OSCARS cascading funding) and eventually maintained/sustained by OBS-PARIS and Strasbourg CDS.
- LOV, used as an example of ad-hoc SAC, is being moved to OntoPortal technology. The resulting platform, LovPortal is to be maintained/sustained by INRAE and UPM.
- DANS SKOSMOS Datastations vocabularies pre-exist FAIR-IMPACT. Discussions are ongoing for future evolution of these services.

The open-source connectors will be maintained by the teams/institutions that have developed them:

- OntoPortal/OpenSilex connector *is to be maintained/sustained* by INRAE MISTEA;
- OntoPortal/Dataverse connector by INRAE DiPSO and the Dataverse open source community;
- OntoPortal/GeoNetwork connector by CNR;
- SKOSMOS/Dataverse connector by DANS and the Dataverse open source community.
- OntoPortal/EasyData connector by BRGM (EasyData provider, external to the project).
- SemData/AgroPortal connector by INRAE URFM.
- EPICHERCHELL/PACTOL connector by AMU.

To scale to another level within EOSC, the topic deserves a dedicated funded action to address and serve a larger number of EOSC communities that either have already started their SAC and are using them for data annotation and interoperability or that are willing/interested to do so. To scale within EOSC, dedicated funding is needed to extend semantic artefact catalogues to more communities, fostering broader adoption of semantic technologies for data interoperability.

2.2.9 MOD and MOD-API

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective

See KER Metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines (Section 2.1.2).

What needs to be sustained

FAIR-IMPACT has published a specification for the description of semantic artefact (MOD) and a reference API for semantic artefact catalogues. MOD (Metadata for Ontology

Description and Publication) is a vocabulary –based on DCAT– developed originally within the RDA Vocabulary and Semantic Services Interest Group (VSSIG) and later adopted by FAIR-IMPACT to semantically describe semantic artefacts and their catalogues ensuring better FAIRness for SAs. MOD-API builds on MOD to specify a REST web service API for SACs, enabling seamless interoperability and unified access to SAs across platforms and domains.

Beyond the project, we shall find a working group mechanism (e.g., RDA, W3C) to maintain and continue this standardisation activity.

Why it needs to be sustained

See the previous arguments related to the Metadata and ontologies KER (Section 2.1.2) and the SAC and connectors KO (Section 2.2.8).

In addition, this KO addresses specifically the following point in the EOSC IF:

- *IF: Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues.* ⇒ FAIR-IMPACT worked to coordinate multiple catalogues into a federated framework. AgroPortal, EcoPortal, EarthPortal and BiodivPortal have been federated. Plus FAIR-IMPACT designed a standard MOD and MOD-API for semantic artefact catalogues to expand beyond FAIR-IMPACT.

Potentially all providers of semantic artefact catalogues (or underlying technology to develop such catalogues) may depend on this KO. In M4.4 (Review of Semantic Artefact Catalogues and guidelines for serving FAIR semantic artefacts in EOSC),⁷² FAIR-IMPACT has established a comprehensive list of these catalogues and technologies potentially concerned by this KO.

Being able to provide and serve semantic artefacts in a standardised, harmonised and coherent manner throughout communities, infrastructures and research organisations is a key aspect in facilitating the use of semantic artefact for FAIR data.

How it is/will be sustained

The sustainability of MOD and MOD-API relies on establishing a long-term standardisation mechanism, in continuation with RDA and potentially within W3C, to maintain and evolve these specifications beyond FAIR-IMPACT. MOD has a strong foundation, having existed before the project and now being adopted as core metadata model inside the OntoPortal SAC technology, and documented on GitHub. By the project's end, the MOD-API is being adopted by multiple SACs, ensuring better interoperability across underlying technologies and long term sustainability of MOD and its API.⁷³ Even in the absence of evolution, MOD and MOD-API specifications will remain usable, serving as a foundation for future standardisation steps. This effort is crucial for EOSC and the FAIR ecosystem, enabling the

⁷² <https://zenodo.org/records/12799796>

⁷³ In the context of the FAIR-IMPACT MOD-API implementation action, 14 SAC providers (including 4 project members and 5 supported by open call), gathered to build the first implementations of MOD-API. At the end of the actions 6 SAC already runs an advanced prototype of their implementation and 5 other ones will be available soon.

harmonised provision and federation of SACs across communities, infrastructures, and research organisations.

2.2.10 FAIR assessment of data

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI”

F. Support adoption of general and domain-specific standards to increase adoption of FAIR practices and develop plans to facilitate reuse (Objective 2).

What needs to be sustained

With regards to the FAIR assessment of data, FAIR-IMPACT produced both metrics and tools. FAIR-IMPACT continued the work done in FAIRsFAIR on the Data Object Assessment metrics, producing a new version of the metrics (v0.8)⁷⁴ based on review and developments in the landscape. Aside from these discipline-agnostic metrics, two sets of discipline-specific metrics have been developed (social sciences⁷⁵, earth and environmental sciences⁷⁶) and implemented in the F-UJI tool for automated data assessment. F-UJI has been further improved and refined based on community review and feedback throughout the project.

Built on the same original metrics, FAIR-Aware has been developed to be increasingly flexible in supporting the creation of new versions based on different metrics, languages, or other focus points.

The original discipline-agnostic metrics, the discipline-specific implementations, the F-UJI tool, and the FAIR-Aware tool all need to be sustained.

Why it needs to be sustained

The FAIR assessment of data allows the ecosystem to gain insights into the FAIRness of their data and improve those levels accordingly. Overall, this increases the availability of FAIR data in the EOSC. This is why metrics and tools to assess the FAIRness of data need to be sustained. F-UJI as a specific tool has seen a great community uptake and relevance.

Before objects can be made FAIR, the involved stakeholders first need to create a sense of understanding of the FAIR principles and their associated practices. This is why evaluation tools like FAIR-Aware are an important contribution to the FAIR assessment landscape. The tool has seen clear continued interest in use since its initial development in FAIRsFAIR and this has continued throughout FAIR-IMPACT. This community need is a clear argument towards sustaining the tool beyond FAIR-IMPACT.

⁷⁴ Huber, R. (2025). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.8). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045911>

⁷⁵ Robert Huber, Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Hervé L'Hours, Joy Davidson, & Hannah Mihai. (2023). D5.1 Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7784120>

⁷⁶ Huber, R. (2025). FAIR metrics for Earth & Environmental Sciences - preliminary results (Versie 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282756>

How it is/will be sustained

UBremen will continue to sustain and develop F-UJI via the F-UJI GitHub repository. Due to the open source nature of the tool, the broad user community is able to contribute through tickets and/or forking to develop the tool to their needs. Given F-UJI's direct relationship to the metrics that it implements, UBremen will continue to evaluate and update the original FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics as the need arises in F-UJI's development. For the discipline-specific metrics, discussion documents have been produced distributed to relevant stakeholders. Those documents which were used within a formal endorsement process have been archived and published via Zenodo, such as the social sciences metrics as part of M5.4.⁷⁷ All metric discussion papers which served as the basis for the further development of F-UJI have been transferred to specific machine readable YAML documents which have been integrated to the main F-UJI code base at GitHub. Thus, sustainability of discipline specific metrics is ensured by UBremen via the GitHub repository as described above, but further development of these metrics is not part of the sustainability plan. The CESSDA Trust & Landscape Working Group will continue to explore F-UJI and the social science metrics in the context of their internal consortium KPI measurements, which could spark a continuation of sustainability conversation later in 2025. Updating the publication of the metrics on Zenodo in the case of new versions will be done collaboratively between KNAW-DANS and UBremen.

KNAW-DANS will continue the care for the original instance of the FAIR-Aware tool. The tool is open source via GitHub and will allow others to create their own versions which they will be responsible to sustain.

2.2.11 Guidelines for transparency

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 2 "Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI"

- I. Promote collaborations between national infrastructures and cross-border initiatives to promote consistent FAIR data standards and enhanced international interoperability (Objective 1).

What needs to be sustained

Task 5.4 in FAIR-IMPACT has developed a set of guidelines and supporting prototypes to promote and illustrate the sharing of repository-related information for a variety of end users in a machine-actionable way. These guidelines are based on well-established standards and schema (DCAT, schema.org) and optionally make use of the FAIRiCAT specification for sharing of repository-level information.

Why it needs to be sustained

⁷⁷ Huber, R., Mihai, H., & Verburg, M. (2023). M5.4 Practical tests for automated FAIR digital object assessment in disciplinary context (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10402148>

The goal of this line of work is to increase findability and interoperability of services and the information they hold, which is of direct and considerable importance for the EOSC ecosystem. Repositories, registries, and other organisations would be able to find and use information from each other with more ease, and subsequently put more trust in each other and the information they offer. The focus area of FAIR assessment makes it possible to better expose assessment results, which impacts the FAIR ecosystem and allows for easier overview of the state of FAIR in the world.

How it is/will be sustained

Discussions are under way to transfer the guidelines and supporting prototypes to the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects⁷⁸ via a formal workshop involving FAIR-IMPACT, FIDELIS, and the EOSC EDEN projects. In the EOSC EDEN project, the resources developed in FAIR-IMPACT Task 5.4 can be further refined and extended to cover a wide range of repository and service attributes and features, and the resulting infrastructure (a registry of repository attributes and features) could be of operational use to the EOSC FIDELIS federation of repositories and services.

2.3 Key Functions

2.3.1 Synchronisation Force

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementation

Strategic Pillar 1 “Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation”

D. Support concertation actions toward greater and more in-depth stakeholder engagement, coordination, governance, and monitoring (Objectives 1 and 3).

What needs to be sustained

The FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force organises annual workshops as a series of online sessions, with representatives from 80-90 initiatives in Europe (and beyond) to assess the progress of work related to FAIR-IMPACT focus areas and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) objectives.

The key function to be maintained is the set-up of this cross-disciplinary, ad-hoc community of stakeholders looking forward to the upcoming meetings and interested in getting informed about updates in the FAIR principles implementation mechanisms.

Why it needs to be sustained

The Synchronisation Force provides a space where representatives of all FAIR and EOSC related initiatives can inform themselves about relevant developments elsewhere in the ecosystem and where ambiguous topics can be discussed in an open and inclusive way. There are no stakeholders that completely depend on the Synchronisation Force function to be able to continue their work. Still, the Synchronisation Force function is highly relevant for a large number of stakeholders in the ecosystem. The value of the Synchronisation Force

⁷⁸ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

relies not just on the assessment of the implementation of the FAIR principles across initiatives and projects, but also, and most of all, on the dialogue and the discussion mechanisms the Synchronisation Force facilitates, by bringing together, for short, 90-minute sessions, actors interested in sharing practices and debating implementation mechanisms around FAIR metrics and assessment, persistent identifiers, metadata and semantic interoperability, FAIR enabling repositories and legal interoperability, as well as the sustainability of project outputs.

The statistics from Zenodo show that the White Papers coming from the Synchronisation Force are highly valued by the community. The White Paper published in 2021, supported by the FAIRsFAIR project, now has 1.250 downloads on Zenodo. The White Paper recently published and supported by the FAIR-IMPACT project was already downloaded over 110 times in less than a month's time.⁷⁹

How it is/will be sustained

The outcomes of the different online workshops are published in concise reports with core findings and recommendations which are shared with the workshop participants and with the community at large. Collectively, these workshop reports form the basis of a White Paper, providing recommendations for alignment and synchronisation around FAIR practices. All proceedings, reports and the White Paper are uploaded to the FAIR-IMPACT community on Zenodo for long-term preservation and sharing.

The mechanisms of the Synchronisation Force will be replicated in the FIDELIS project,⁸⁰ namely in the “Strategic alliance” workshop series, planned from 2026 on (in October 2026 - M22, February 2027 - M26 and August 2027 - M32) as three online workshops with EOSC landscape projects, data– infrastructures and international initiatives. The topics addressed during the sessions will be different, based on FIDELIS objectives, but the cross-disciplinary, ad-hoc community engagement approach will be maintained.

Furthermore, a blueprint with different scenarios for continuation of the Synchronisation Force function was produced and published on Zenodo. This blueprint can be used by other initiatives, like the EOSC Winterschools, or projects that would like to continue the Synchronisation Force Workshops, run by the FAIRsFAIR and FAIR-IMPACT projects.

2.3.2 EOSC FAIR Champions

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 1 “Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation”

F. National policymakers should support Research Infrastructures, e-infrastructures, and national service providers to align activities and establish EOSC support structure (Objectives 1 and 3)

⁷⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/5744786>
<https://zenodo.org/records/14979705>

⁸⁰ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

H: Support professional development programmes to ensure research support staff have the required data stewardship and information security management skills (Objective 1).

What needs to be sustained

FAIR-IMPACT established and mobilised a group of 13 EOSC FAIR Champions⁸¹ that actively run until the end of the project in May 2025. The EOSC FAIR Champions have been engaged in many different ways in the project activities (events, deliverables and document production and authoring, facilitators with regional and thematic communities, evaluators of open call applications) and recognised themselves as such. Their contribution is acknowledged in FAIR-IMPACT publications and results.

Why it needs to be sustained

The EOSC FAIR Champions are individuals who advocate for the adoption of the FAIR principle while working on a daily basis at their own institutes. Some of them are Data Stewards too. They are key drivers of EOSC and FAIR implementation mechanisms, tools, and practices and have a key multiplier effect given their role, authority and recognisability within disciplinary and country-based research communities.

How it is/will be sustained

Establishing a forum where the EOSC FAIR Champions could continue to meet and debate would be useful to keep their engagement active. This could be done in the framework of bottom-up initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA), or in the framework of new projects such as OSCARS. EOSC FAIR Champion profiles could be published and linked from the EOSC Partnership country webpages. Having a legal entity issuing the label of “EOSC FAIR Champion” (i.e., the EOSC Association) would give value to the visual recognition stated by the FAIR-IMPACT project. A blueprint with lessons learnt and recommendations for building and managing similar groups of Champions and ambassadors will be delivered by May 2025 as part of *D7.3 Impact report [dissemination, exploitation and communication results]* and published as a stand alone document, available from the Zenodo FAIR-IMPACT community.

2.3.3 National Roadshows

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objectives and MAR implementations

Strategic Pillar 1 “Sustaining and enhancing the EOSC Federation”

F. National policymakers should support Research Infrastructures, e-infrastructures, and national service providers to align activities and establish EOSC support structures (Objectives 1 and 3).

Strategic Pillar 2 “Contributing to the web of FAIR data and the uptake of AI”

⁸¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/eosc-fair-champions>

I. Promote collaborations between national infrastructures and cross-border initiatives to promote consistent FAIR data standards and enhanced international interoperability (Objective 1).

What needs to be sustained

The series of National Roadshows was conceived as online or on-site events with the aim of speeding up FAIR adoption by communities in different European countries, thanks to the engagement with local facilitators who are chosen strategically to identify the topic of the event, the target community and the channels for promotion.

Why it needs to be sustained

The roadshows extend the network of projects and initiatives that FAIR-IMPACT already collaborates with, introducing another platform to promote FAIR-IMPACT recommendations, good practices, and assessment tools. These roadshows were a key instrument to engage the national level stakeholders, which were an explicit focus of the FAIR-IMPACT project for community engagement.

How it is/will be sustained

FAIR-IMPACT started a “National Roadshow Blueprint document” to provide suggestions and guidance on how to organise such a series of workshops. Information about resources needed to organise the series can be added to this, to help quantify the investment, as well as lessons learnt from the organisation of such events, and recommendations to enroll national level communities. Examples of linkages between national roadshows and the NLI support programmes will also be included, as a remark for decision makers and NL initiatives to follow up from where FAIR-IMPACT ended. Originally included in *D7.3 Impact report [dissemination, exploitation and communication results]* due by May 2025, this guidance document will be published as a stand alone document, made available on Zenodo and shared with initiatives and projects interested in bringing this effort forward.

As it happens for the entire FAIR-IMPACT community, participants to the National Roadshows can also be contacted by FAIR-IMPACT Data controller and data processors beyond the end of the project, to invite them to contribute to national initiatives or for other outreach activities that third party initiatives want to pursue, including the EOSC Association or follow-up projects like EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS.

2.3.4 Forum related to semantic artefacts, their catalogues, mappings and governance within EOSC

This output can be mapped to the following SRIA objective

See KER Metadata and ontologies recommendations and guidelines (Section 2.1.2).

What needs to be sustained

This corresponds to the ‘forum’ function FAIR-IMPACT took on to discuss semantics with scientific communities within EOSC and beyond. This includes semantic artefact catalogue

advocacy and support for EOSC communities, the discussions related to mappings, and governance or adoption of semantics and metadata in general.

Why it needs to be sustained

See the previous arguments related to the Metadata and ontologies KER (Section 2.1.2) and the SAC and connectors KO (Section 2.2.8) and the MOD and MOD-API KO (Section 2.2.9). This KF is the forum to enable the continuation of the outreach and adoption of work on metadata and ontologies. Any data stakeholders dealing with metadata and ontologies are directly concerned with the KF.

How it is/will be sustained

Sustainability will rely on various RDA groups, including a new WG on FAIR mappings, and continued engagement from partners. The OntoPortal Alliance will partially take over support for communities adopting semantic artefact catalogues. Initiatives like the annual OntoPortal Workshops or the OntoPortal federation both established during FAIR-IMPACT will contribute to long term support of this function. To maintain this forum, which is essential for ensuring continued dialogue and progress on semantic interoperability within the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems, further EOSC projects focused on semantics are also needed.

Discussions with respect to semantics shall continue in the context of the new EOSC Task Force and Technical and Semantic Interoperability as well as Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 (Metadata, ontologies and Interoperability) set up by the EOSC Association and in which project members are already involved.

3 Recommendations for the future

Many project deliverables provide input into future actions that are required to move the EOSC/SRIA/FAIR practices forward, but are beyond the scope of the project themselves. In many cases we have negotiated for these actions to be included in the planning of institutions or future projects. However, the above shows that certain elements require further centralized investment in the future. To give one concrete example: to scale within EOSC, dedicated funding is needed to extend semantic artefact catalogues to more communities, fostering broader adoption of semantic technologies for data interoperability (see 2.2.8).

In section 1.4 of this report the sustainability session that was part of the Synchronisation Force Workshop series 2024 was described. The conclusions from that session that was attended by a diverse group of stakeholders from projects, the EOSC Association as well as the European Commission, provide valuable recommendations for the future.⁸² They are listed below.

There is general agreement that the planning towards sustainability should start early in a project's lifetime, involve all partners, and be dynamic and flexible as the project advances. Each project also produces a unique collection of outputs in a unique context and therefore requires a tailored sustainability plan. However, there are common challenges and opportunities that all projects should be supported in.

The EOSC federation has a crucial role for the EOSC related projects' sustainability pathways. However, while many projects work to create solutions for EOSC or advance EOSC in some way, EOSC still remains to a certain extent a moving target and is currently not yet available for the integration, endorsement or uptake of these solutions. This forces the projects to consider other (temporary) sustainability solutions, and runs the risk of work not being sustained at all and never contributing to EOSC in its intended way. Furthermore, shifts in the environment are very challenging for projects to respond to within the limits of their agreed work. The more security and clarity projects can get on the (near) future from the steering bodies like the European Commission and EOSC Association, the more they can navigate and try to be flexible with their solutions. It is also important to note that community uptake is not easily achieved without European Union and/or EOSC endorsement. This should be kept in mind when considering alternative sustainability options.

A first version of the EOSC Federation Handbook was recently published. It documents the decisions taken by the EOSC Tripartite Governance on the EOSC Federation and serves as the reference document for the operation of the EOSC Federation. This handbook could play a role in the provision of project sustainability by incorporating or referencing guidelines, recommendations, policies, etc. produced in the context of projects.

⁸² Everhardt, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Horton, L., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., Grau, N., Rouchon, O., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). M1.9 Third Synchronisation Workshop Report - 20250211_Graphical version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848907>

Based on the experiences of a collection of previous projects, the idea was raised to capture recurring challenges, possible solutions, and other recommendations or processes in a sustainability handbook. Networking events like the EOSC Winter School could be places to discuss and collaboratively create such an output.

Based on these insights the session participants formulated three overall recommendations:

- The EOSC Association should consider incorporating and/or referencing relevant outputs from EOSC-related projects in future versions of the EOSC Federation Handbook;
- The EOSC Association and the EOSC-related projects should start a dialogue to identify potential sustainability pathways for project outputs (possibly during the Winter Schools);
- A Sustainability Handbook should be created to capture the common challenges, possible solutions, and experiences from previous projects in a way that provides useful references for new projects considering sustainability.